

their hybrids 1984-87. Morphological traits of Lu Dao are more similar to the japonica land varieties.

Seed set of the hybrids of Lu Dao and the japonicas was higher than that of Lu Dao and the indicas. Lu Dao's easy shedding and long blackish awns are dominant in F₁ progeny. The F₁ plants from Lu Dao and the japonicas showed higher pollen fertility when Lu Dao was used as female parent.

Esterase analysis of embryos indicated that the esterase isozyme bands of Lu

Dao were similar to those of the two japonica varieties. One esterase band of Lu Dao, absent in the indica varieties, appeared in all F₁ hybrids tested.

Cytogenetic studies showed that chromosomal aberrations such as 10 II + 1IV (1.47-2.51%), univalents (0.42-2.66%, range 1-4 per cell), laggards and straggling chromosomes (0.89-1.54%), bridges and fragments of chromosomes (0.72-3.61%), and some multivalents were common at metaphase I and

anaphase I in F₁ PMCs (see table). Aberrant chromosomal pairing in the F₁ of Lu Dao and the japonicas appeared to be somewhat lower than in Lu Dao and the indicas. This might indicate more chromosomal structural differences between Lu Dao and the indica varieties.

This analysis suggests that Lu Dao is an intermediate type of rice germplasm, between *O. sativa* L. ssp. Keng Ting and *O. rufipogon* Griff. □

Dominance relationship and nature of genetic variances for yield and its components in rice

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We crossed 10 divergent rice cultivars (Mahsuri, Dhaneswar, Pawanpeer, Adamchini, TAU 18, Kanakjeera, IR50, IR52, IET7552, IET4140) in all possible combinations (excluding reciprocal) in 1982. Parents, F₁s, and F₂s were raised in a compact family randomized block design with three replications.

Plot size for parents and F₁ was one row; for F₂, six rows of 20 plants each at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Data were collected on days to panicle emergence, plant height, panicle length, effective tillers/plant, grains/panicle, chaff seeds/panicle, 100-grain weight, and grain yield/plant.

Means for 15 plants of parents and F₁ and 50 plants of F₂ per replication were subjected to graphical analysis, component analysis, and combining ability analysis of diallel crosses (see table).

Mean dominance degrees estimated through graphical, genetic component, and combining ability analyses differ in

some characters. Combining ability analysis is the most reliable; results of graphical and component analyses may be seriously affected by correlated gene distribution and/or presence of epistasis. □

Dominance relationship and nature of genetic variance for yield and yield components.

Character	Generation	Degree of dominance		
		Graphical analysis	Component analysis (H ₁ /D) ^{1/2}	Combining ability analysis (2σ ² _g /σ ² _s)
Days to panicle emergence	F ₁	Overdominance	Overdominance	Additive
	F ₂	Partial dominance	Complete dominance	Additive
Plant height	F ₁	Partial dominance	Partial dominance	Additive
	F ₂	Partial dominance	Partial dominance	Additive
Panicle length	F ₁	Partial dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive
	F ₂	Partial dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive
Effective tillers/plant	F ₁	Partial dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive
	F ₂	Partial dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive
Grains/panicle	F ₁	Partial dominance	Complete dominance	Additive
	F ₂	Complete dominance	Complete dominance	Additive
Chaff seeds/panicle	F ₁	Partial dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive
	F ₂	Complete dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive
100-grain weight	F ₁	Partial dominance	Partial dominance	Additive
	F ₂	Partial dominance	Partial dominance	Additive
Grain yield/plant	F ₁	Partial dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive
	F ₂	Complete dominance	Overdominance	Nonadditive

Genetic divergence in upland rice

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We evaluated 23 drought-resistant cultures from Kerala and Tamil Nadu, India, and IRRI during 1987 wet season for their genetic diversity, using Mahalanobis D² analysis.

The varieties were sown in a randomized block design with three replications. At harvest, 15 plants were selected at random from each plot to measure plant height, productive tillers, boot leaf length and breadth, and yield.

Using Tochers' clustering technique, the genotypes were grouped into six clusters (Table 1). Seven of eight genotypes in cluster I (from IRRI) showed much less variability in their genetic architecture. Cluster III includes types from different geographical regions.

The clustering pattern failed to indicate any relationship between geographic divergence and genetic variability. The genotypes from Tamil Nadu fell into different clusters. The

Table 1. Composition of D² clusters showing genetic diversity.

Cluster	Genotype
I	Brown gora (IRRI), BR319-1 (IRRI), OS4 (IRRI), IR12979-24 (IRRI), C22 (IRRI), UPLRi-7 (IRRI), Kala-keri (IRRI), PM1128 (Paramakudi)
II	20A (IRRI), OS6 (IRRI), UPLRi-5 (IRRI), N22 (IRRI), Charupuncha (Kerala), PMK1 (Paramakudi), Arurakhari (Kerala), PM1381 (Paramakudi)
III	Azucena (IRRI), Kattanur (Ramnad), Norungan (Ramnad), MDU1 (Madurai)
IV	E45 (IRRI)
V	IR9575 Sel (IRRI)
VI	Moongil Samba (Kerala)

Table 2. Intercluster and intracluster genetic distances.

Cluster	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
I	90.52	37.92	65.21	37.68	47.70	165.67
II		92.61	44.38	43.24	39.98	122.32
III			47.38	79.12	38.96	65.50
IV				-	85.84	190.89
V					-	97.31
VI						-

wide genetic variability of genotypes of the same origin might be due to varied phenological conditions.

On the basis of intercluster D² distance, clusters I, II, IV, and VI were highly divergent (Table 2).

Use of the genotypes in these clusters, particularly E45, IR9575 sel, and Moongil Samba, in breeding programs could result in high heterosis for qualitative and quantitative characters. □

Pollen development and hybridization between indica varieties of rice

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We crossed four indica rices—IR36, Pant Dhan 4, Rasi, and IET7301—in all possible combinations. Pistils hand pollinated with pollen from dehiscing

Pollen germination and pollen tube growth 60 min after pollination and seed set in crosses of different rice varieties.^a Pantnagar, India.

Cross	Pollen germination (%)	Pollen tube growth (μ)	Seed set (%)
IR36/IR36	61.00 (4)	602.0 (2)	29.8 (4)
Pant Dhan 4/Pant Dhan 4	72.00 (2)	532.0 (7)	35.2 (2)
Rasi/Rasi	85.00 (1)	591.2 (3)	34.8 (3)
IET7301/IET7301	70.00 (3)	502.0 (9)	35.7 (1)
IR36/Pant Dhan 4	55.50 (6)	546.4 (5)	17.2 (8)
Pant Dhan 4/IR36	19.00 (14)	505.0 (8)	02.6 (16)
IR36/Rasi	25.00 (13)	556.4 (4)	04.6 (14)
Rasi/IR36	51.00 (8)	405.0 (13)	24.7 (7)
IR36/IET7301	37.00 (11b)	542.0 (6)	07.8 (13)
IET7301/IR36	37.00 (11a)	430.0 (12)	08.9 (10)
Pant Dhan 4/Rasi	53.00 (7)	495.0 (10)	25.4 (6)
Rasi/Pant Dhan 4	37.00 (11c)	362.0 (15)	08.3 (12)
Pant Dhan 4/IET7301	34.00 (12)	398.0 (14)	08.5 (11)
IET7301/Pant Dhan 4	46.90 (9)	996.0 (1)	03.3 (15)
Rasi/IET7301	60.00 (5)	493.0 (11)	29.2 (5)
IET7301/Rasi	44.40 (10)	320.0 (16)	10.2 (9)

^aNumbers in parentheses = descending order of values for each character.

anthers of male parents were collected 60 min after pollination. Pollen grain germination and pollen tube growth were studied with normal microscopy of squash preparations of pistils in aniline blue.

Onset of pollen germination was variable in all individual crosses, but was similar in all selfings (see table). Maximum pollen germination was obtained with selfing. Pollen germination in all reciprocal crosses except IR36/IET7301 differed considerably.

Pollen fall on stigmas of each individual floret varied. In some crosses, 20-30 pollen grains could be seen on the stigma; in others, only 5-6. Emergence of pollen tubes on the bifurcated hairy stigma occurred immediately after pollen grains had landed on the stigma. After penetrating the papillated stigma hairs, the tubes grew through these hairs into the style (see figure).

Styles were quite long and the pollen tubes could not be traced up to the base (staining became faint as pollen tubes worked their way toward the ovary). Pollen tube growth differed considerably in the reciprocal crosses. There was no abnormal pollen tube growth and no evidence of pollen tube and maternal tissue interaction hindering growth.

Overall, seed set was quite poor. Maximum seed set was with selfing.

Normal pollen tube growth of IET7301/Pant Dhan 4 10 min after pollination. Pantnagar, India.

Pollen germination was correlated more directly with seed set and was not affected by the rate of pollen tube growth (see table). Seed set was highest in IET7301/IET7301: that cross had the third highest pollen germination and ninth longest pollen tubes.

The reciprocal crosses confirmed that correlation. When IR36 was crossed with Pant Dhan 4, pollen germination was 55.5% and seed set was 17.2%; in the reciprocal cross, pollen germination was 19% and seed set, 2.6%.